

THE ACTION OF CHLORINE ON THE HYDROXIDES OF IRON AND CHROMIUM IN THE PRESENCE OF IODINE.

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By passing a brisk current of chlorine through a boiling solution of iodine in iron (ic) hydroxide and chromium hydroxide, $\text{FeIO}_3, 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 22\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were obtained respectively.

Bahl and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 168, 398) have studied the action of chlorine on the hydroxides of lithium, potassium and alkaline earths. They found that in the case of alkali metal hydroxides, periodates are formed while in the case of alkaline earth hydroxides, iodates are formed. We have taken up the present work on the same lines and have found that in the case of the hydroxides of iron, periodates of the composition, $\text{FeIO}_3, 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and of chromium, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 22\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are formed respectively.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Freshly prepared hydroxides of iron (Fe^{III}) and chromium were taken in suspension in water and powdered iodine was added to it. A brisk current of chlorine was then passed through the hot suspension of iodine in the hydroxides. In the case of ferric hydroxide a light brown precipitate was formed, whereas a clear solution was obtained in the case of chromium hydroxide by the above treatment. On adding alcohol to the clear solution formed in the case of chromium, a green precipitate was obtained. The precipitates were filtered, washed with hot water, and dried at 400° . The green precipitate of chromium was found to be insoluble in water like most of the periodates. Metals were determined as oxides. Iodine and available oxygen were estimated by methods adopted by Partington and Bahl.

TABLE I.

Iron salt.

Sample No.	Iron.		Iodine.		Available oxygen.	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	12.04%	12.14%	27.80%	27.54%	12.20%	12.14%
2.	12.04	„	27.70	„	12.40	„
3.	12.00	„	27.75	„	12.20	„

These results correspond to the formula $\text{FeIO}_3, 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$. This salt has also been obtained by the interaction of ferric salt with potassium periodate (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise in Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1922, Vol. II, p. 416).

TABLE II.

Chromium salt.

Sample No.	Chromium.		Iodine.		Available oxygen.	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	8.05%	8.12%	39.70%	39.69%	17.50%	17.50%
2.	8.20	"	39.89	"	17.40	"
3.	8.35	"	39.83	"	17.50	"

These values correspond to $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{I}_2\text{O}_7, 22\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The ratio of iodine to oxygen is 2 to 7.

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